

USING LANGUAGE TEACHING METHODS

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Annotation: This article deals with the concept of teaching methods in the English language. The process of learning foreign languages in modern world is becoming an indivisible component of the professional training of different profits and the development of contacts with foreign partners largely depend on the quality of their language training.

Key words and expressions: Language teaching methods, general methodology, goals, technique, organizational forms of teaching, professional training.

The very best language educators can often be identified by their commitment to creative and innovative classroom teaching strategies. They are constantly trying new language teaching methods to engage their students and experimenting with new teaching tools to improve learning outcomes.

These language teachers understand that there is no quick fix that they can deploy to help students quickly fluent in their target language. Instead there are some common, evidence-based teaching approaches which can help make a difference. This blog post summarizes 10 of the most notable approaches to language teaching. We hope that they will support language educators looking for some inspiration to improve their teaching practice.

1. The Grammar-Translation Method

This is a very traditional teaching approach which priorities translation from the students' mother tongue into the target language and vice versa. To succeed in

this approach, students need to memorize long lists of vocabulary and detailed grammar formats and rules. The approach favors accuracy over fluency and tends to favor the development of reading and writing skills instead of speaking skills. The downside of this approach is that it does not prepare students with spontaneous communication skills. Classroom activities therefore usually include grammar drills, vocab tests and encouraging students to incorporate new grammar concepts in standardized writing tasks.

The frustration experienced by the limits of the Grammar Translation Method in terms of its inability to create communicative competences in learners gave rise to direct method. This revolution began towards the end of 18th century. The teaching of foreign and second language began to be approached along language acquisition perspective.

2. The Audio-lingual Method

This way of teaching was developed in response to some of the problems associated with Grammar-Translation. As a result, classes are usually held in the target language as this approach deliberately seeks to prioritize speaking and listening skills. Activities typically involve students repeating the teacher's words (either face to face or through headphones in a language lab) until they get the pronunciations and rhythm right. Good work is rewarded by educators and mistakes are quickly corrected. In the early to mid-1900s developments in other fields example psychology, behaviorism has had a great effect on language teaching resulting in the audio-lingual method. The audio-lingual method has students listen to or view tapes of language models acting in situations. Students practice with variety of drills, and their instructor emphasizes the use of the target language at all times. The audio-lingual method was used by the United States Army for crash instruction in FL during World War II. Despite the documented success of these programs, they are no longer common. The start of the mid-1960s is distinguished by a range of theoretical challenges to the audio-lingual method. Linguist Noam

Chomsky challenged the behaviorist model of language learning. He proposed a theory called Transformational Generative Grammar, as per which learners do not acquire an endless list of miles but limited set of transformations which can be used over and over again, (e.g, a sentence is changed from affirmative to a negative sentence by adding not and the auxiliary verb.) so that the language learner can form big number of sentences.

3. Communicative Language Teaching Method

Communicative language teaching/learning (CLT/ CLL) can be interpreted in many different ways and used to describe a wide variety of classroom procedures, because it refers to a diverse their correspondence between columns. Communicative teaching language is widely used all over the world. A brief description of CLT is value-laden and direct transposition of this method and its principles carry the ideological value about choice, freedom, and equality that are not universal. According to P.N. Sullivan, Western set of rather general and uncontroversial principles. We sum principles pointed by J.C. Richards (Richard J.C) and basic characteristics of this approach. It is worth to compare values will reflect not only in principles of CLT but also in common CLT classroom activities and practices, such as pair and group work, and information gap activities. For mentality of learners from Eastern and Asian countries freedom of choice and equality and others in the EL classrooms are not appropriate. Effective classroom activities will necessary pair and group work in information gap activities, but activities that fit the students' discourse styles. Depending on the cultural, or even the physical setting, a teacher can use tasks, pair and small group learning or the whole class format. The Silent Way is a discovery learning approach, proposed by Galeb Gattegno in the 50s of the last century. It is often considered to be one of the humanistic approaches. It is called The Silent Way because the teacher is usually silent, leaving room for students to talk and explore the language. It is often

associated with Cuisenaire rods and wall charts where words are colour-coded; each phoneme a different colour.

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